

FACTORS PREDISPOSING SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS TO JUVENILE DELINQUENCY

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the role of guidance and counselling in the Nigerian secondary schools system. It examined some factors predisposing secondary school students to juvenile delinquency. Factors like the family, the media, culture, substance abuse and peer group influence. The writer concluded by suggesting some ways in which these factors could be prevented or controlled. Based on the above findings, the researcher recommended, among others, that the appropriate authorities should organized cultural seminars to inculcate morals on juveniles thereby making them better citizens. Parents, government and counsellors should enlighten youths on the negative effect of the above predisposed factors. (The family, the media, culture, substance abuse and peer group influence)

Keywords: *Juvenile, Delinquency, The Family, The media, The culture, The substance, The peer group influence*

Introduction

Throughout the history of mankind, there have been many different people and professionals who have become confidants and helpers to persons who have sought assistance, who have been less fortunate than others or who have simply needed the comfort of a friend. Hence guidance in the past was seen as “directing”, “assisting” and “guiding” which was a service rendered by the head of the families, parents, priest in the church, Imams of the Muslim faith, older sibling, etc. This contention supports Gibson and Mitchell (2003) posit, that the first counterpart of professional counselling were perhaps the elder of ancient tribes who advised the youths and guided them towards responsible decision and behaviour. Hence, in ancient times, helping relationship between people probably focused on the development of fundamental skills for survival.

Different definition of guidance and counselling have been presented by scholars of different school of thought and there is no one definition of guidance and counselling that satisfies the intellectual discipline of all guidance counsellors. Guidance and counselling have three generally accepted components: educational guidance, vocational guidance and personal counselling. The three components are part of pupils’ personal services.

Miller (1988) in his book: “Guidance Principles and Services” defined guidance as a process of helping individual to achieve self-understanding and self-direction necessary to make home and community. Guidance is a programme of service to individual students based upon the

needs of each student, understanding of his immediate environment, the influence of the factors on the student and the unique feature of each school. It is designed to help each student adjust to his environment, develop the ability to set realistic goals for himself and improve his total educational programme (Issikson and Mink, 1963).

Odebunmi (1991) sees guidance as a helping service which is designed to help individuals within the school setting and those outside it to realize their fullest potentials, emotionally, morally, socially, academically and vocationally growth of development. From the above definition, it is clear that guidance, whether viewed as a concept or service is a programme that is designed to assist individual in his totally development or it is a process of information given to an individual, thus providing him with a diversity of choice. It is in the light of the above, Idowu (2000) definition of counselling as a formal interpersonal relationship between two persons (a counselee and a client) in other to find solution to problems

UNESCO (2002) defined counselling as actively listening to and individual story and communication understanding, respect and empathy clarifying goals and assisting individuals with the decision making process. Thus counselling is a mutual relationship between a counselor, a professional trained helper and a client.

Guidance and counselling have positive approach toward solving disciplinary problems among pupils at various schools.

In conclusion of the introduction part, Guidance and counselling can be seen as a process in which persons are directed and informed on how they are to live their lives within their immediate environment and the larger society.

The Role of Guidance and Counselling In the Secondary School System.

The need for guidance and counselling services in the secondary school has increase with the introduction of the new educational system 6-3-3-4. Without counselor, the new system of education will surely be a flop because it will seem like operating a complicated system in a vacuum. Hence the guidance counselor should work hand in hand with other teachers in their vocation choice.

Omotosho (2002) stated that the place of guidance and counselling in Nigeria schools, cannot be overemphasized with the introduction of the 6-3-3-4 system, school certificate examination result, unemployment and increasing cost of schooling among others.

In view of the apparent ignorance of many. Young people about career prospect, officers and counselors shall be appointed in post primary schools. Since qualified personnel in this category are scarce, government shall continually make provision for the training of interested teachers in guidance and counselling. Guidance and counselling are also necessary in teacher education programme. Proprietors of schools should provide guidance counsellors in adequate numbers in their secondary schools.

Therefore a viable programme of carrier guidance in the school system of education will help students develop awareness of their self in relation to the world of work. The practice of guidance and counselling in school will ensure that student benefits fully from the educational system.

What Is Juvenile Delinquency?

Juvenile Delinquency simply refers to any anti-social criminal act performed by juveniles (young persons who have not attained adulthood).

New Webster's Dictionary (1981), defined juvenile delinquency as a law violating behaviours of person legally defined as minors. Legally, Juvenile delinquency comprises two distinct types of behaviours: Criminal activities committed by youths (robbers, cultism, murder, examination malpractice or rape) and Activities prohibited to children but not to adult such as truancy, running from home, curfew violations or incorrigibility as known as status offences.

Blessing (2012), defined it as youth crime which is usually beyond parental control and is therefore subjected to legal action. At times, they are also referred to as deviants because their behaviours are anti-social and illegal.

There are many schools of thought as to the predisposing factors that contribute Secondary School Students to Juvenile Delinquency. Most of these are tied to nature and nature augment. It is certainly the case of children who are neglected, abuse or impoverished are more likely to fall into delinquency acts. Though this may be statistically relevant if it fails to account for the delinquency of those who have good and loving parents, and suitable living circumstances. Geneticists are refuting the idea that children are tabularize or blank state. This make up may play a factor predisposing Secondary School Student to Juvenile Delinquency.

Juvenile delinquency has been identified as a social malady, and in view of this, many researchers have risen up to the challenges of suggesting some factors that lead to it and how it could also be curbed. The question is what are the factors that predispose someone to become a Delinquent?

For the purpose of this research, the following factors will be reviewed.

1. Family
2. The media
3. Culture
4. Substance abuse
5. Peer influence

1. Family

One of the most important factors influencing delinquent is the family setting. It is within the family that the child internalizes those believe values, attitude and general pattern of behaviour that gives direction to subsequent behavior. Most Nigeria parents hardly have time for training their children due to the pursue of materialism. The effect of such parental neglect is that children will not have proper sense of direction. The family unit is crucial to a child development and healthy upbringing. In addition, most of what a child learns is through the family or guardian.

2. The Media

Television and movies have popularize the cult of heroes "which promote justice through the physical elimination of enemies. Many researchers have condemned that young people who watch violence films tend to act more aggressively, or violently, particularly when provoked. This is mainly characteristic of eight to twelve years old boys who are more vulnerable to such influences.

Media brings an individual to violence in three ways: First, movies that demonstrate violence and excite spectators, and the aggressive energy can them be transferred to everyday life, pushing an individual to engage in physical activities on the street. Secondly,

television and newspaper can portray ordinary daily violence committed by parents or peer. This is also applicable to internet. American psychological association has revived the evidence and has concluded that television violence account for about ten percent of aggressive behavior among children.

Delis (2005), added that the pornographic films, magazines, newspaper and television have strong bearing on the moral decadence of youth in secondary schools.

3. **Cultural Factor**

Cultural factor could also be termed “band wagon “effect. The band wagon has many applications. The tendency to follow the action or belief of others can occur because individual desire information’s from others.

Giutierenez and Rogoff (2003), see education as the need to understand individual histories and ideologies, as well as the culture patterns and belief of groups. Delinquent behaviour often occurs in social setting in which the norms for acceptable down under such circumstances many of the common rules that deter people from committing socially unacceptable acts may lose their relevance in the society. They respond to the trauma ting and destructive change in social reality, by engaging in rebellious demand of criminal activities.

4. **Substance Abuse or Drug Abuse**

Indiscipline is the distortion of controlled moral or mental behavior. It may also refer to the intentional refusal to follow rules and regulations of a given society. The above define aspect is too rampant in the youth and students of today. This fully may explain why many of the prison and police cell are filled with the youth.

According to Carroll (2000), drug is any substance which entering the body can change either the function or structure of the person. On the other hand drug abuse is a situation where drug is taken more than it is prescribe. It can also been seen as the use of illicit drugs or the abuse of prescription by youth substance or drug abuse is undoubtedly the most common risk factors. Ten years ago (10 years) the situation was very much better but today, youth are more exposed to powerful drugs even children studying in elementary schools are not safe.

They have easy access to illegal powerful drugs since these minors often do not have enough money to buy drugs, they become addicted to and commit crime to obtain money.

5. **Peer Influence**

Youth policy reflects an understanding of the role of the peer group as an institution of socialization. Membership of a delinquent gang, is like membership of any other natural group which can be part of the process of becoming an adult through such primary association, an individual acquires a sense of safety and security. Develop knowledge social interaction and can demonstrate such quality as loyalty or leadership. In adult private welfare, a number of studies have shown that juvenile gang members consider their group a family.

In some areas those who are not involved in gangs continually face the threat of assault, oppression, harassment or extension on the street or at peer group have always had its attendant problem for both parents and teachers as far as discipline is concerned. Young adolescent spend a great deal of time with people belonging to their own group. The value and attitude of these set of friends within the peer group. This tend to become an improved influence on behavior.

Characteristics of a Delinquent Child

Delisi (2005) attributed the following characteristics to the delinquent child.

1. Physically, he is very muscular in the body. An appearance that makes him unique and gives him a sense of pride
2. Temperamentally, he is not only impulsive and distinctive, if given an ample opportunity to exercise his inherent traits.
3. Attitudinally, he is hostile, defiant, stubborn and non-submissive to authority. These are to be expected because he sees himself as an authority whose power are not subservient to another.
4. Intellectually, he is subnormal since he has nothing to offer to others who are not within his authority.
5. Educationally, he is backward with low intellectual capability. Educational progression will not be only be difficult, but mission impossible.
6. Sexually he is crudely exploitative with little or no affection. The delinquent cannot relate with members of the complementary sex lovingly.
7. Morally he is incapacitated since the delinquent belongs to a sub-culture that is governed by self made rules, his moral outlook must be difficult from that of the large society.
8. Socio-culturally, he is unstable and affectionless since the sub-culture he grew up has no specific influence on him.
9. Socially, he is always at home with an organized violent gang.

Conclusion:

From this study it can be concluded that the above mentioned factors; family, media, cultural factor, drugs abuse and peer influence predispose secondary school students to juvenile delinquency henceforth an intervention programme that involve all major stakeholders in education process students teachers, parents, government, counsellor and psychologist should continue to intensify to ensure good learning experience where students can learn and efficiently so that laudible aim and objective of setting up schools can be meant

Recommendations:

Since juvenile delinquency exist in secondary schools, it is therefore important to make the following recommendation:

- (1) It will be of high value if the government and non-governmental organization in conjunction with community to enlighten the youth on the negative effects of breaking law in order to reduce or eliminate this delinquent acts.
- (2) Parents and teachers should take proper care of children. They should realize that children must be given a sense of direction, love affection and every support they need both in school and home.
- (3) Parents and the law makers should take a great scrutiny of our cultural values; this should be with the aid of expunging those that are not important to humanity.
- (4) The mass-media agents, particularly the television authority should preview their programmes first, before showing them.

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